

THE CREOL NATIONAL PROJECT AND THE SEGREGATION OF INDIGENOUS PEOPLES: LITERARY CONFLUENCES IN FOUNDING LATIN AMERICAN TEXTS OF THE 19TH CENTURY

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ABSTRACT

Under the influence of positivism, different projects of the Nation-State in Latin America in the 19th century were consolidated in forms of government that were constituted from the creole oligarchic groups that maintained colonial social and political privileges and that, at the same time, segregated different indigenous peoples. The term *creole* is used here under an ethnic approach to indicate the white-mestizo group born in America as a result of miscegenation between local inhabitants and Europeans who came to settle in colonial lands and who generated descendants. In this perspective, the present research was proposed in order to analyze the thoughts of several intellectuals of politics and literature of this period who valued the emergence of new governments from the republican ideals related to the oligarchies composed by the mestizo/creole groups descended from the conquering white peoples, excluding slaves and their descendants, Indians and other minorities from social and political life. Among these intellectuals, names like Simon Bolívar, José Inácio de Abreu e Lima, José Henrique Rodó, Domingos Faustino Sarmiento and José de Alencar stand out who, when writing the different Latin American founding texts, sought in European molds the basis for the social, cultural, political and economic structures that disseminated in the continent a highly excluding worldview towards indigenous peoples and other minorities that did not fit into the thinking and national projects proposed by the thinkers and leaders of the hegemonic classes that governed the then former Hispanic colonies and Portuguese .

Keywords: Creole national project. Latin American founding texts. Segregation of indigenous peoples.

INTRODUCTION

The 19th century permanently marked the cultural and political structures of the American continent through the independence movements, especially in Latin America, a factor

reflected in history and literature. With the economic and social development of the new independent States, different political movements sought European models as the basis for their social structures, a factor that enabled a wave of migratory movements that had a great influence on the historical formation of Nation-States in the Americas under a strictly nationalizing prism that is based on both the formation and creation of so-called creole peoples. The term creole is used in this work to indicate the “natives of a region, who are formed through ethnic crossings between different local groups, with foreigners, or even with foreign peoples who came to settle in the place, in order to generate certain offspring” (ROIZ, 2012, p. 110) who constitute themselves as mestizos.

From this perspective, artistic-cultural production is consolidated based on different founding texts intrinsically related to the genesis and continuity of ethnic and national identities with works that we understand to be historically located in the transition between colonial literature until its emergence in the emergence of national literatures. in Latin America in the 19th century. Political and literary thinkers of this period valued the emergence of new governments based on democratic ideals represented by oligarchies composed of mestizo/creole groups descended from the conquering peoples, excluding from social and political life slaves and their descendants, Indians and other minorities. From this perspective, throughout the 19th century, several works have addressed the issues of indigenous remnants from the perspective of segregation in contrast to the emancipation of people in America reflected in the forms of government of the colonies that constituted themselves as Nation-States. Among the most influential names in Latin American culture and literature, it is possible to highlight Bolívar (1999), Sarmiento (1874), General Abreu e Lima (1855) among others, whose works predicted the segregation of indigenous peoples in order to proclaim the natural disappearance of these individuals and other minorities.

1. Positivism in Latin America and the National Project: The Spanish-American Creole Supremacy in Bolívar, Abreu e Lima and Rodó

Having suffered strong influences from Comte's positivism (1798-1857), Latin America invested in the scientific and economic development of society , with this philosophical current being understood “as an indivisible set, mental organization, the importance of intellectual activity as responsible for evaluating history progressive development of the human spirit, knowledge as social intervention in addition to the absence of opposition between science and religion”. (SANTOS, 2015 p. 380). From the perspective of Sommer (2004), positivism in Latin

America is configured as an eclectic tradition that combines a reverence for the positive or scientific, reflected in the current context in the use of empirical data through the association between social sciences and natural sciences, especially biology, favoring “the identification of social ills, diagnosing them correctly and remedies were prescribed accordingly” (SOMMER, 2004 p. 94).

Regarding positivism in Latin America and the consolidation of national projects, several names have made relevant contributions in politics and literature, which we highlight from Domingo Faustino Sarmiento (1811-1888) in Argentina, José Enrique Rodó (1872-1917) in Uruguay, José Inácio de Abreu e Lima (1794-1869) in Brazil, among others. In the Latin American context, positivism is proposed as a synonym for modernity based on Western models that sought to exalt civilization and deny the autochthonous origins of American nations. For Santos (2015, p. 284-285), positivism fulfilled a double role in Latin America that it sought:

[...] ideologically organize the nascent national democracies and provide Latin Americans with a system of ideas and customs that surpassed the social and psychological forms considered old, new ideas and ways of life that stimulated material progress and the industrious habits of their population. Only in this way would there be an organization of the chaos that the Colony experienced after Independence.

In this way, positivism in Latin America is configured as a current that opposes theology, metaphysics and philosophy through critical thinking and establishes itself as widespread in the name of science and that is established in “belief and material progress based on development scientific and utilitarianism were seen as systems suitable for industrial life” (SANTOS, 2015, p. 386).

Thus, the formation of Latin American nations sought a structure that emphasized positivism as a striking expression of scientism with a strong cosmopolitan tendency centered on capitalist interests typical of the European model, a source of inspiration for American thinkers. Therefore, themes such as science, race and civilization should be part of national values, influenced by the European *modus vivendi that were centered on evolutionary, scientific and Darwinist theories*. However, it is worth noting that these European models considered to be evolved “were models used in different ways by intellectuals, which provided a diversity in the way of viewing cultural evolution” (SANTOS, 2015, p. 389) in the different nations of America.

Regarding Latin American positivism, Santos (2015, p. 392) states that Rodó (1872-1917) is one of the great representatives of this movement. Rodó (in: SANTOS, 2015) states

that, after the independence process, Latin America transformed into divided and quartered societies in a process in which the feeling of loss of place in the world was established and the idea of integration became the condition that most defined the continent. In this context, Pérez (1981) states that the first nations consolidate themselves as a State around a region, an independence movement and around a leader and consolidate themselves as a "nation is a historical category" (PÉREZ, 1981, p. 3).

For Correia (1966), the territory and the Latin American people merge, transform and present themselves as "a generally accepted phenomenon that, between the 17th and 18th centuries, the native stopped feeling Spanish (we could also add Portuguese) and started to consider himself American" (CORREA, 1966, volume VII, p. 373) . In Rodó (SANTOS, 2015), the republic dreamed of by José Martí (1853-1895) would be built on the idea of freedom, prosperity and peace, but it was also intelligence, culture and idealism and these feelings would be the American political and social basis, maintaining also a position favorable to maintaining the continuity of the spirit of tradition, which was characterized as a process of decharacterization of ideas and cultures. It is worth noting that, in the consolidation of the national project in Latin America, some social groups would be excluded from this process, such as gauchos, blacks and Indians. For Sommer (2004), under the motto of cultural evolution in America from the popularization of Spencer's theories (1820-1903), a type of organization was proposed that conceived human history in a progressive scheme of stages that, associated with significant growth in modernization and Europeanization, "the most radical ideologues defended a policy that combined white immigration with the removal of Indians or blacks" as Sommer (2004, p. 94) warns us.

In Brazil, based on a Darwinist conception of society, Abreu and Lima (1855) stated that the Indians, due to their genetic and even social nature, were doomed to disappear. For Abreu e Lima (1955, p. 252):

[...] it seems to us that the predominance of the Caucasian race has been fully demonstrated; just as brutalized races tend to disappear due to the expansive force of modern civilization, not through conquest or bloodshed, but because nature expels them from the surface of the earth, where there is no longer any place for them. To fill the void, which they must leave, the same nature makes incomprehensible efforts reproducing the most energetic race, and making it, so to speak, cosmopolitan.

Still for Abreu and Lima (1835), the ideal of population perfection was that of the United States of America and stated that the American people "5/6 are perfectly homogeneous, without a mixture of different classes" (ABREU E LIMA, 1835, p 56). For the aforementioned author,

Brazil was relatively behind compared to the United States. Thus, Abreu and Lima (1855) stated that indigenous races would tend to disappear given the configuration of the Brazilian national project, being replaced by Caucasian groups arising from the migratory processes characteristic of the cosmopolitan nature typical of Latin American positivism. The biological and social conditions and even the very political nature of the Indian would place him in the “condition of an inert class, and of no political weight” (ABREU E LIMA, 1835, p. 56) doomed to disappear. For the aforementioned author, this would be a natural process characteristic of colonized nations and he cites as an example, among many others, the Anglo-Saxon people who developed in an “astonishing way in America, following the same progress in Great Britain” (ABREU E LIMA, 1855, p. 252) whose migratory groups greatly increased the American population.

From a political approach, Bolívar (1783-1830), when questioning the forms of government of the American countries that were in the condition of Spanish colonies, argued that political rights should be left with the mestizo peoples (creoles) to which he himself made part. In this way, Bolívar proposed:

But we, who barely preserve traces of what once existed, and who, on the other hand, are neither Indians nor Europeans, but an intermediate species between the distant landowners of the country and the Spanish usurpers; in short, we being Americans by birth; and our rights are those of Europe, we must contest them with those of the country, and we must stand against the opinion of the invaders; thus we find ourselves in the most extraordinary and complicated case. (BOLÍVAR, 1999, p. 10).

However, for Bolívar (1999), indigenous leaders would be left out of the governments of the new American states, since the Creole with European rights should be given control of the hitherto colonies. From this perspective, Almeida and Raminelli (2011, p 115) state that “the Creole nationalist discourse praised the Inca past while despising the Indian of the present”. To combat the Inca forms of government, Bolívar in 1925 issued a decree that extinguished the chiefdom and consequently the Inca nobility. For Méndez Gastelumendi (1996), Tupac Amaru's rebellion in Peru was followed by a gradual extinction and delegitimization of the indigenous nobility in addition to hardening the Creole stance towards the Indian. Bolívar was directly related to the various prohibitions given to indigenous peoples in Peru, including any and all types of demonstrations that could revive Inca traditions. Thus, Méndez Gastelumendi (1996) states that the reproduction of Inca symbols and traditions was taken over by the Creoles, in a stylized way to neutralize any political content that could be exposed by the natives. Still for Méndez Gastelumendi (1996), the interpretation of the Tupacamarist revolt seen as a

nationalist movement can be understood from the perspective of Creole supremacy, as even the revolution itself was considered Creole-mestizo, removing any reference to the indigenous character of the conflict.

Thus, based on the above and through the different views on the figure of the Indian and his representation in Latin American literature (fictional or non-fictional) of the 19th century, we are led to believe that, in the configuration of the independent states of Latin America, in the consolidation of independent nations in their different national projects, the aim was to establish the Creole – generally of descent, born in colonial lands that maintained their European political rights – in political control by exploiting indigenous labor and excluding them from the control of different ethnicities that shaped the Latin American social framework.

2. Sarmiento, the Argentine National Project and Indigenous Barbarism

In an attempt to establish the integration of the provinces that surrounded the Rio de la Plata, a group of intellectuals known as Nueva Generación emerged with names such as Juan Bautista Alberdi and Domingo Faustino Sarmiento. These conceived of the territory that made up the Silver Provinces in Argentina as a region that constituted a “territory without integration, each one more resembling a fiefdom, and was closely associated with the notion that the society existing in the country was not civilized” (MOREIRA, 2010, p. 74) and presented themselves as barbarians. Focusing on the need to consolidate and unify the territories of the regions that faced the southernmost part of the country and were under indigenous control, there was a geopolitical interest in incorporating them into the Argentine national project, leading to the Conquest of the Desert campaign that sought to incorporate of Patagonia to the jurisdiction of the State in order to solve what Sarmiento (1874) understands as an indigenous problem.

Thus, for Santos (2018, p. 5), “Sarmiento believed that the extermination of the Araucanian indigenous people to the south would be a natural process, whether from military conquests or from contact with the whites” that would occur in the period known as the Desert Conquest campaign (1881). In the consolidation of the Argentine national project, the search for economic, social and cultural development from a Eurocentric vision, new ways of conceiving life in society were proposed, permanently modifying the relationship between the individual and society. In the Latin American cultural and artistic context, Perrone-Moisés (1995, p. 251) that, through the constitution and affirmation of local cultures and literatures, “idyllic relations with France began to sour, and numerous voices were raised against this then called dependence.” Already in the middle of the century. XIX, several controversies occurred

and were fought between those who defended a more authentic national literature and those intellectuals who supported a literature open to European influences where barbarians (indigenous people) were opposed to the civilized ones (white Argentine elite).

For Iturri (2007, p. 27), Sarmiento was linked to the political use of the word through literature that sought the imposition of civilization in the face of barbarism, a barbarity represented by groups of Indians, blacks and Argentine gauchos. For Sarmiento, literature has a state function and is carried out by reformulating social relations in the text, and seeks to homogenize the specific knowledge of marginalized areas to reduce their diversity to the discourse of central power. Still for Iturri (2007), Sarmiento states that literature operates within the borders of National States, especially in Latin America and acts not only through the ability to culturally modernize a particular nation, “but that this work was part of an Americanist project of cultural homogenization” (ITURRI, 2007, p. 29) as a national project that seeks in Europe the bases of American culture, excluding from Sarmiento's homogenizing project some of the minorities from marginalized areas, such as the Indians. It is in the context of cultural homogenization that Sarmiento stands out. For him, the Argentine national project is consolidated based on the “search for scientific knowledge that would mark the search for a characteristic Argentine evolutionism distinct from the rest of Latin America” (SANTOS, 2018, p. 08) that would combat social diversity and miscegenation since different social areas, such as gauchos, blacks and Indians, were attributed as responsible for the internal destabilization of Argentina.

In his works, Sarmiento developed a thought that defends the need for white Argentine ethnic unification and stated that “the hostile and barbaric environment of provinces distant from Buenos Aires should be neutralized in favor of modern civilization” (SANTOS, 2018, p. 6) . Marginalized areas such as Indians and even mestizos would be, for Sarmiento, the cause of the historical weakness of Latin America since “the presence of 'pure races' was associated, in his thinking, with democratic stability and the absence of despotic governments with the civilized world as a comparison” (SANTOS, 2018, p. 6). Thus, Sarmiento's national project sought to reproduce the European *modus vivendis* through white Argentine ethnic routes as an intellectually superior race in behavior and habits compared to indigenous peoples. With this we understand that, for Sarmiento, through social, political and economic growth, in addition to the process of territorial unification of Argentina, some indigenous groups were doomed to disappear. From a critical perspective, Santos (2018, p. 5) states that Sarmiento's ideas:

The aim was to build a civilizing social model, whose origin was imagined to be independent and with peculiarities in white Argentine society, but which

had its origins in European and North American societies at that time. Racism, in a way, became institutionalized at this time with public insults towards indigenous and black people in Sarmiento's writings. Among his various works, we particularly highlight *Conflicto de Razas* (1883), at the height of the 1880 movement.

In this context, the idea of race was disseminated across the Latin American continent, where “political discourse, social thought, medical and scientific research, literature, journalism and various other intellectual manifestations made indiscriminate use of it, to the point of intending to use it to defend radically opposite ideas”, a factor observable in the various works of Sarmiento (1874), such as *Facundo: Civilización i Barbarie*, a fiction that consolidated the opposition between the terms civilization (Indians, blacks, mestizos) and barbarism (Argentine white race) and which influenced Latin American thought in the second half of the 19th century. In *Facundo*, Sarmiento (1874, p. 116) writes in a critical tone about the Indians in a highly prejudiced way, as in the example: “[...] el día que pasaron la cordillera hubo una escena patética. Era necesario bajar las armas y no había manera de concebir a los indios que vivían en países donde no se les permitía llevar un arma en sus manos”. We understand that for Sarmiento, wild populations were socially backward, averse to democracy, economic progress and education and civil liberties, and were therefore barbaric and responsible for the backwardness of the Argentine nation. Throughout *Facundo: Civilización i Barbarie* (1874) we realized in Sarmiento that any act of discrimination and war was justified against the Indians and other minorities. In this context, he radically criticized the then compatriot president Juan Manuel de Rosas for establishing agreements with indigenous peoples preserving their agrarian possessions. On this topic, in a footnote to *Facundo: Civilización i Barbarie*, Sarmiento writes that:

Rosas prohibits the government of the border from undertaking any expedition against the Indians, allowing them to periodically invade the country and even more than two hundred leagues from the border. This is what Rosas did not do before as he had done so in the last part of the expedition, the results of which were ephemeral, leaving the evil subsistent, which has taken on even greater aggravation than before (SARMIENTO, 1874, p. 131)

It is observed that Sarmiento harshly criticizes the position of then Argentine president Juan Manuel de Rosas regarding the agreements made with indigenous peoples. The Indians are presented as a social evil whose rights should be curtailed due to the social and economic development of Argentina. Still for Sarmiento, the great problem of the American continent was “the existence of these savage populations” (SANTOS, 2018, p. 8) that were opposed to democracy, economic progress, civil liberties and education itself, seen as characteristic

features of civilized societies. Thus, Sarmiento (1875, p. 114) concentrates a critical tone that is not free from prejudice/racism when conceptualizing the Argentine indigenous people using the term “barbarism”, describing them as the “uneducated savage of the Pampas”.

Sarmiento's program for Argentina is both modernizing and whitewashing society. Modernizing based on the economic and capitalist model of the United States of America in the sense of republican and secularizing ideas that “[...] generated a new way of conceiving social relations in Argentina. His studies on individualism, within a Darwinist and positivist context, would be the embryo of a nationalist formation” (SANTOS 2018 p. 9). The process of whitening Argentina will occur as a result of Sarmiento's attempt to bring white European immigrants to Argentina, since, for Sarmiento (1874, p. 15) “the French nation has been the crucible in which the modernity.

3. Conclusive Summary

The analysis presented above was based on the reflection of some of the most influential names in politics and literature regarding the segregation of indigenous people in Latin American literature in the 19th century without, however, disregarding the important role of the aforementioned historical figures presented above in the cultural, historical, social and literary consolidation of Latin America. From this perspective, we observed that, in parallel with the consolidation of independent nations in South America, some groups were segregated, among which we highlight different ethnicities from different countries such as Brazil, Colombia, Chile, Argentina, among others. Still for Abreu e Lima, the past of advancement had given way to the degeneration of the race, aligned with the thinking of intellectuals such as Bolívar, Rodó, Sarmiento in what was believed to be the decadence of the American continent and the indigenous people.

In the context of the segregation of indigenous peoples in Latin America, Méndez Gastelumendi (1996), states that it is not just any Indian who is despised, but those who did not remain in their 'legitimate' place and indigenous subjection is necessary for the preservation of the 'legitimate' place. national integrity', an idea that was understood from politics to literature in the 19th century. Thus, with regard to nationalism in Peru, drawing a parallel with creolism in other Latin American countries, from the end of the 18th century onwards, “a fundamental rejection of the indigenous element” was established in the Hispanic colonies (MÉNDEZ GASTELUMENDI, 1996 , p. 206), this rejection being one of the bases of nationalism in Latin America in the 19th century. Méndez Gastelumendi (1996) states that, based on the debates that

began in the 19th century regarding the silencing and segregation of Latin American indigenous peoples through a grand rhetoric of rejection of everything indigenous, a new thought emerged in the 20th century with regard to the new configurations of national projects that supported the emergence of a nation-state with a predominantly indigenous ethnic composition.

It is in this context that some of the social and artistic movements emerged in the 20th century, such as indigenism, as an artistic and cultural current that opposed the old colonialist and even post-colonialist current of the 19th century that represented the indigenous as a reflection of the interests of dominant creole classes since “indigenism has living roots in the present and draws its inspiration from the protest of millions of men” (MARIATEGUI, 2008, p. 317) and assumes a testimonial character and denounces the oppression and segregation of indigenous peoples occurred in previous centuries. Thus, influenced by a contrastive position, different historical and artistic currents that promoted the reappropriation of indigenous themes in Latin American Literature, history and culture throughout the 20th century and reverberate until our present.

5. REFERENCES

ABREU E LIMA, JI **Bosquejo historical, political and literary history of Brazil** . Nictheroy, Typographia de Rego e Comp., 1835.

_____. **Socialism** . Universal Typography. Recife. 1855

ALMEIDA, Cecília; RAMINELLI, Ronald (org.). **History of the Americas: New Perspectives** . FGV Editora. Rio de Janeiro. 2011

BOLIVAR, Simon. **Charter of Jamaica** . Ática Publisher. São Paulo. 1999

CORREA, GV **The formation of Hispanic American nationalities as a cause of independence** . In: **International Congress of American History** . National Academy of History. Buenos Aires. 1996

ITURRI, Guillermo Mariaca. **The power of the word: essays on the modernity of Hispanic American cultural criticism** . Tajarar Editores. Santiago – Chile. 2007

MARIATEGUI, José Carlos. **Seven essays on the interpretation of Peruvian reality** . Trans. Felipe José Lindoso. São Paulo: Expressão Popular/CLACSO, 2008.

MÉNDEZ GASTELUMENDI, Cecília. **Incas sí, indios no: notes creolenationalism in Peru and its contemporary crisis** . Free Translation. Journal of Latin American Studies , (Cambridge University), 28, February 1996: 197-225

MOREIRA, Marcelo Sevaybricker. **Immigrants and Argentines in the civilizing process:**

an analysis of the political thought of Alberdi and Sarmiento . In Thesis: UFSC Electronic Magazine. v. 7 – n. 1/2 – January-December/2010

PÉREZ, J. Space and National Identity in Latin America . In: **Essays on the formation of national consciousness in Latin America** . National Center for Scientific Research. Paris. 1981

PERRONE-MOISÉS, Leyla. Paradoxes of literary nationalism in Latin America . ADVANCED STUDIES. In: **VALDÉS, Maria Elena. VALDÉS Mário J. YONG, Richard A.** (eds.), **Latin America as its literature** , New York, Council on National Literatures, 1995

ROIZ, Diogo da Silva. From American creolism to São Paulo mameluco: processes of independence and formation of the state and nation in Alfredo Ellis Jr. Revista de Ciências Humanas, Florianópolis, Volume 46, Number 1, p. 109-122, April 2012

SANTOS, Rafael Macedo da Rocha. Domingo Sarmiento's thoughts on the formation of the Argentine nation . Historiar Bulletin, vol. 05. No. 04, Oct/Dec 2018, p.03-12

SANTOS, Elisângela da Silva. Indivisible Latin America: the influence of positivism on José Enrique Rodó's intellectual project. Sociologias, Porto Alegre, year 17, no 40, Sep/Dec 2015, p. 380-414

SARMIENTO, Domingos Faustino. Facundo: civilization and barbarism on the Argentine pampas . Libreria Hachette y Cia. Paris-FRA. 1874

SOMMER, Doris. Foundational Fictions: The National Novels of Latin America . Belo Horizonte: UFMG, 2004.